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ALL ABOUT
RESPECT

Project Report

Dr Nathalie Noret¹
Dr Susan Hillyard^{1,2}
Dr Melanie D. Douglass²
Dr Anna Macklin²

¹University of York

²York St John University

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Background

Gender-based violence and Hate Crime are frequent experiences for young people. According to the National Audit Office (2025), in 2022/23, 20% of recorded crime was associated with Violence Against Women and Girls (VAWG). Gender-based violence in young people is a global issue and is a function of gender inequality in society (Scottish Government and COSLA, 2018). It includes behaviours such as sexual harassment, sexual assault, stalking, partner violence and rape (Equally Safe at School, 2025). There is also overlap with hate crime (crimes that are perpetrated based on someone's actual or perceived identity, CPS, 2016), where misogyny has been included in the definition of hate crime in North Yorkshire since 2017 (North Yorkshire Police, 2022).

As young people develop, they are exposed to new freedoms and environments while negotiating new social relationships with reduced parental monitoring. Therefore, young people are at particular risk of experiencing gender-based violence and hate crime as they navigate these new social experiences. For example, in schools, young girls may be contacted by several boys at night with requests for nude/ semi-nude images, and young boys report regularly receiving sexual images and videos that they did not want to see (Ofsted, 2021). Such experiences develop a culture where such behaviours are normalised to the point of being an expected part of daily life.

Strategies that educate young people on gender-based violence are, therefore, desperately needed. As UN Women (2024) suggested various methods that could be used, including the empowerment of young people to talk about the issues, and challenge rape culture. Such interventions are needed to **"shape the way they [the next generation] think about gender, respect, and human rights. Start conversations about gender roles early on, and challenge the traditional features and characteristics assigned to men and women"**.

The All About Respect project creates a space for open and honest dialogue about healthy relationships in young adults. The project brings together individuals and organisations committed to tackling gender-based violence and hate crime in York and North Yorkshire.

Working collaboratively with young adults (aged 16-25), we aim to design campaigns and training that are evidence-based and youth-led.

All About Respect 2023-2025

In the 2023/24 and 2024/25 academic years, we have worked with young people aged 16 to 25 in education to raise awareness of gender-based violence and hate crime and raise awareness of how to tackle this behaviour. Working with young people, we have worked in a collaborative and creative manner to seek their understanding and opinions on: 1) what is gender-based violence and hate crime, and 2) what young people think we can do to tackle this behaviour. To achieve these aims we have held...

- **Campaign Stalls** tied in with national and international campaign weeks (e.g., 16 Days of Activism and National Stalking Awareness Week), including activities to involve young people.
- **Social Media campaigns** to disseminate key points and findings as part of our campaign activities.
- **Focus Groups and Surveys** to gather data on young peoples' opinions and experiences.
- **An Artivism competition** inviting young people to create art representing healthy and unhealthy relationships.
- We have also delivered **bystander intervention training** to highlight how young people can challenge this behaviour.

This report

This report presents an overview of our work over the past two years, alongside highlights of the data provided by young people. Including:

1

Analysis of our campaign day data, including young peoples' 1) perceptions of safety in York, 2) understandings of healthy relationships, and 3) perspectives on what can be done to tackle gender-based violence and hate crime.

2

Submissions to our Artivism competition, which explored young peoples' artwork on gender based violence, , and healthy (or unhealthy) relationships.

3

Key findings from our focus groups, which aimed to examine young peoples' understandings of gender-based violence and hate crime, alongside their ideas on what can be done to tackle this behaviour.

4

Key findings from our survey of young people. The aim of the survey was to examine young peoples' attitudes toward and knowledge of gender-based violence and hate crime, alongside their experiences of these behaviours, their reporting behaviours and the impact of their experiences. The survey was not designed as a prevalence study, but rather to explore the nature and impact of these experiences on young people.

We present our data in sections, drawing together data on 1) Knowledge and understanding, 2) Feeling Safe, 3) Experiences of gender-based violence and hate crime, 4) Reporting Experiences, and 5) The Impact of gender-based violence and hate crime. The final section summarises the key findings and next steps in our All About Respect project.

Our work

This section of the report provides a summary of the work we have undertaken over the course of the project and the number of young people who have participated in our project activities.

Our Work

Through our work, we have engaged with young people through our range of activities. We have...

Held 22 events during 16 days of activism, anti-bullying week, hate crime week, Sexual Violence Awareness week, alongside ad hoc events.

Engaged with 1,075 young people through our campaign events.

Involved young people in our Artivism competition.

Engaged with 4,925 people through our social media and webpage campaigns.

Conducted Focus Groups with 14 young people.

Conducted a survey of 193 young people aged 16 to 25.

Young Voices

Our online survey was completed by 193 young people aged 16 to 25.

Note: Percentages may not total 100% due to missing data.

Knowledge & Understanding

In this section of the report, we summarise the findings from our work on young peoples' knowledge and understanding of gender-based violence and hate crime and what we can do about these behaviours. These findings are drawn from 1) our survey results, 2) our Artivism competition, 3) our Focus Groups and 4) our campaign day activities. Please see pages 7 and 8 for an overview of how many young people were involved in these activities.

Knowledge and Attitudes

In our survey, we asked young people about information they may have received regarding gender-based violence and hate crime . The key findings from these questions are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Reports of receiving information on gender-based violence and hate crime.

Note: GBV = Gender-based violence, HC = hate crime.

Knowledge and Attitudes

Our survey also asked about young peoples knowledge and attitudes towards gender-based violence and hate crime. The key findings are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Reports of receiving information on gender-based violence and hate crime.

Note: GBV = Gender-based violence, HC = hate crime.

“ I am not a very strong person. I am short and weak, and I struggle with conflict. I like to think that I would do my best to intervene if I saw harassment/violence, but I am not sure that I am brave enough.

“ I believe it is very difficult to prevent violence as individuals without the right support systems such as communities and the law enforcement taking people seriously.

Knowledge and Attitudes

Our survey also asked young people about their perception of educational activities/ programmes and support services focused on tackling gender-based violence and hate crime in the area, see figure 3.

Figure 3: Reports of receiving information on Gender-Based Violence and Hate Crime.

Knowledge and Attitudes

Young peoples' attitudes toward relationship violence were also examined in the survey. Reassuringly the majority of young people responded negatively (disagree/ strongly disagree) towards the permissive attitudes. Here we present the prevalence of the more permissive attitudes, see Figure 4.

Figure 4: Permissive attitudes towards relationship violence

4.7% (N=9) agreed with the statement that *"someone who makes their partner jealous on purpose deserves to be hit"*.

7.8% (N=15) agreed with the statement that *"there are times when dating violence between couples is ok"*.

9.9% (N=19) agreed with the statement that *"Sometimes, violence is the only way to express your feelings"*.

5.7% (N=11) agreed with the statement that *"Some couples have to use violence to solve their problems"*.

Artivism

Art can be a powerful way to spread important messages and raise awareness of challenging social issues. Over the course of our project, we have held several Artivism competitions, inviting young people to submit their artwork representing gender-based violence and hate crime. This artwork then features in our campaign work, training, and awareness raising work on social media. Below you will see two previous winners of our Artivism competition.

We launched our most recent Artivism competition in 2024. Entrants are invited to submit their work and share what their work represents. The submissions and artist narratives are shared on the following pages.

We would like to thank all those who contributed to the Artivism Competition.

Your creative pieces show us how powerful art can be in illustrating the fears felt by young people when facing violence in their everyday lives.

Dress

My favourite dress is adorned with buds
 Their delicate petals bloom when basked in sunlight
 Revealing a precious centre at heart.
 A fragrant aroma escapes
 It diffuses and permeates the air

Enticing bees.

At first,
 The bee appears harmless
 Until enigmatic remarks twist my perception
 The bee reveals himself a threatening predator-
 Starved of youthful nectar

Fleeting eyes cause
 Stings to successively strike my skin
 The flowers on my dress wilt and shrivel,
 Killed by his poison laced actions.

The dress hangs.
 Lifeless, limp

Scars torment and harass me
 They cling to my body but remain invisible

Scars. That should have never been formed
 Scars. That shall incessantly endure ...

“

It's a poem about unwanted male attention (especially by older men received by a young girl) and also sexual harassment. It also focuses on the effects of sexual harassment and the shame that the receiver may feel when they shouldn't.

”

“

This artwork is inspired a lot by Little Red Riding Hood and how she is chased by a wolf. So in this case, it's a woman in a red dress (little red riding hood) being chased by her attacker (the wolf) and she hides in a lift. And lifts are notoriously known places where women get assaulted, so I wanted to show that with a real picture of a lift to show that this does happen in real life. And lastly the eyes signify how women feel like they are being looked at all the time (even one looking up her skirt as it's unfortunately something women have to go through), and shows she's going through a panic attack. It also adds to the creepy atmosphere. I added a darker mood lighting to set the tone of fear and feeling trapped.

”

“

I think most women will know when they see what is a relatively unassuming image of a fist holding keys, what it means to carry your keys between your knuckles. To me, that's what it is to be conditioned to expect harassment and violence, and prepare for it. My dad didn't know what it represented. My mum immediately did.

”

“

My painting expresses the panic of crossing the road when there is rude and intimidating young men.

”

“

My painting is about walking home in the dark. The tree at the end of the pathway is Home, which is why it's 'safe' looking (the only one with leaves). The trees on either side are lifeless with sharp, jagged branches. They are designed to look scary because the walk home in the dark is scary. The reason for that can be found in between the trees. The path to the green tree is being watched from all sides by over a dozen eyes, red to symbolise that they are all potentially dangerous because none of them should be there. There is no safer path to take; the only way home is to walk through the watching eyes and hope for the best.

”

Focus Groups

Alongside our survey, we are also conducting focus groups with young people to examine 1) how they understand and talk about gender-based violence, relationship violence, and hate crime, and 2) what we can do to tackle these behaviours in our community. The initial analysis has identified the themes summarised below.

Young people discussed **a range of behaviours** when discussing gender based violence and hate crime, including street harassment, assault and problematic behaviours in relationships. Young people also highlighted terms not commonly used, such as *hoovering* (“being forced/ sucked back into a destructive relationship”).

Participants raised concerns about **gender-based violence on the internet and on social media sites**, with fears about online Incel culture. Young people were left with a sense of powerlessness on how to stop or challenge the material they were being sent or viewing.

Normalisation: Lots of the young people highlighted that gender-based violence and hate crime were so normalised and an expected part of life. This was particularly the case online, where young people talked about the prevalence of inappropriate image sharing.

Not knowing whether or how to report experiences was flagged as an issue young people face when reporting gender based violence and hate crime. This became a barrier to reporting as it was not perceived as easy to do.

Age-appropriate education was highlighted as a real need at an ever-younger age. Participants highlighted that they don't want just to be talked at, but the need for engaging activities to teach about these challenging behaviours.

What can we do?

As part of our campaign stalls, we run an activity where young people can share their thoughts on how we can tackle gender-based violence and hate crime in our community. Young people are invited to write on our Doodle Boards and share their thoughts and ideas. Figure 6 shows a summary of the analysis of these comments. The comments clustered around four categories: 1) taking personal responsibility, 2) a need for greater collective social responsibility to tackle these issues, 3) more early education to foster respectful interactions and 4) more preventative solutions across our community.

Figure 6: Reports of what young people think we can do to tackle gender based violence and hate crime.

Keep your hands to yourself!

Educate men.

♂
♀
Respect goes both ways ♀
♂

Feeling Safe

In this section of the report, we summarise the findings from our work on young peoples' perceptions of feeling safe in York and North Yorkshire. These findings are drawn from 1) our survey results, and 2) our stall activities. Please see pages 7 and 8 for an overview of how many young people were involved in these activities.

Feeling Safe

Data from our survey suggest that the majority of young people reported feeling safe in York and North Yorkshire, with approximately 10% reporting feeling unsafe or very unsafe, see Figure 7.

Figure 7: The proportion of young people who report feeling safe in York and North Yorkshire

Feeling Safe

The majority of young people reported feeling safe in York and North Yorkshire, with many students stating that they feel safer in York than where they grew up. Comments regarding feeling unsafe related to Gender-Based Violence, Racism, Homophobia/ Biphobia, particularly related to going out on an evening. Examples of these comments are shown below.

I feel mostly safe especially during the day, but there are certainly sometimes on an evening or night out where I feel on edge.

In general as a woman do not always feel 100% safe, particularly at night when walking alone or past men

Gender based crime is quite high at the moment in my area; spikings, verbal and physical assaults etc. It makes me nervous around people, especially at night.

York is small and cosy, and I do feel safe living here; however, recently I have been a bit worried about leaving my house as a non white person.

Sometimes i worry about racial violence and being jumped.

I feel unsafe on public transport in my area, I also feel unsafe in my college at times.

Feeling Safe

As part of our campaign stalls, we also conducted a 'where do you feel safe' activity where young people were asked to place a red sticker where they feel unsafe and a green sticker where they feel safe. Figure 8 shows an example of this activity. Common areas of feeling unsafe include the river, around the snicket areas off Grape Lane and Petergate, around McDonald's, and by the bus station.

Figure 8: Feeling Safe Activity

Feeling Safe

As part of the feeling safe activity, young people were provided with the opportunity to share their thoughts on why they do not feel safe in specific areas in York. The common themes are shown in Figure 9. As this figure shows, common themes included: 1) particular vulnerable spaces such as by the river, 2) poor lighting and concerns about darkness, 3) fears related to public transport in particular buses, 4) the impact of alcohol, and 5) those in roles related to security (e.g., doormen) not tackling particular issues.

Figure 9: Key points from the *Feeling Safe* Activity

Experiences of gender-based violence and hate crime

The following section of the report provides an overview of young peoples' experiences of gender-based violence and hate crime.

The findings are taken from our survey.

Please see page 8 for an overview of the number of young people who participated in our survey. We provide a breakdown of the prevalence of different forms of violence experienced alongside direct quotations from young people. The survey also gave young people the opportunity to expand on their answers. The direct quotations in this section of the report are taken from these survey questions.

Sexual Harassment

Overall, 56.6% of our survey respondents reported experiencing sexual harassment, As shown in Figure 10 the most commonly experienced behaviours were 1) unwanted sexual jokes, 2) unwelcome sexual comments and 3) unwanted sexual gestures.

Figure 10: The proportion of young people who reported experiencing sexual harassment

Sexual Harassment

Young people were provided with the opportunity to share their experiences of sexual harassment, we have shared some of these incidents below. The majority of young people shared the nature of the behaviour experienced, alongside where the incident occurred.

“ I was walking on the road, when this guy started calling me and wanted to touch my boobs and ass ”

“ A guy tried to initiate sexual and flirtatious conversations with me while I was just trying to complete a group project for my uni course with him and others. ”

“ Someone groped my bottom in the middle of a night club, and I don't know who did it. No one else saw or noticed it happen but I told my friends and they moved me into the middle of our group so I was 'protected' and I told friends after the night who were sympathetic but felt the same as me that nothing could be done. ”

“ Mostly being cat called or being touched inappropriately on a night out. ”

“ It [*the harassment*] was on a type of website where people are allowed to show off their bodies. ”

Stalking

The survey also captured young peoples' experiences of stalking. As shown in Figure 11 the most commonly experienced stalking behaviours were 1) communication via social media sites, 2) calls and text messages and 3) trying to solicit personal information from other people.

Figure 11: The proportion of young people who reported experiencing stalking

Stalking

Young people were provided with the opportunity to share their experiences of stalking, we have shared some of these experiences below.

“
Called me over 30 times, made fake social media accounts, got their friends to text me and pretend they were someone else.
”

“
He refused to leave me alone even when I had entered a new relationship and went as far as contacting my mum to get information on me and my new relationship. The only thing that made him stop was my boyfriend contacting him directly and after that he completely backed off.
”

“
Once blocked, he would find me on different platforms to continue messaging me.
”

“
It was a coworker messaging me in quite a sexually suggestive way following a work night out and wanting to see me, but I have a long term partner.
”

“
They followed me home then found me on messenger and was spamming my messages.
”

Relationship Violence

From our survey, 60.1% (N=116) reported currently being in a relationship. Further, 17.6%, (N=34) had experienced relationship violence since September 2023, 23.8% (N=46) had experienced partner violence before September 2023, see Figure 12.

Figure 12: The proportion of young people who reported experiencing partner violence

Relationship Violence

Young people were provided with the opportunity to expand on their experiences, and we share some of this detail below.

“ I suppose we were a little toxic at first because we were both so young and had no experience of being in an intimate relationship that things were done like snooping on each other's phones, or having arguments. ”

“ My now ex partner had been really aggressive and made attempts to physically attack me. ”

“ Felt okay within the context, talked through with partner to understand why, explained feelings and worked through it. ”

“ Criticising me and bringing up prior incidents in the manner it was done was not an incident that needed to be talked about and was not done in an abusive way. ”

“ An ex continued to perpetuate these [aggressive] behaviours against me even after we broke up. ”

Sexual Assault

Our survey also asked young people whether they had experienced sexual assault. Overall, 16.1 % (N=31) of young people reported experiencing sexual assault since September 2023. Young people were provided with the opportunity to share their experiences and we have provided examples below.

“ I have had two experiences; one with a new partner I was dating- they pushed to have sex even though I said no and overpowered me, I ended things after it happened. The second with a first date; they kissed me and tried to push my hands down to touch them sexually even though I said no multiple times. I ended up leaving and didn't speak to them again. ”

“ I was groped in the middle of a night club, someone put their hand up my skirt and groped my bottom. ”

“ Under the influence of alcohol and unable to prevent it. ”

“ When I was 17 at a friends party we had all gone to bed and another invited person got into bed with me and started to touch me - after the shock I managed to leave but no-one took me seriously afterwards. ”

Hate crime

In the final section on victimisation, we asked young people about their experiences of hate crime. The prevalence of experiencing hate crime is shown in Figure 13, and below are some of the experiences shared by young people.

Figure 13: The proportion of young people who reported experiencing hate crime

“ I have been called slurs by strangers when going through town, I was wearing a pin badge with my chosen pronouns on it and they harassed me for it, I was called numerous names and my physical appearance was mocked. ”

“ A hate crime regarding my religion. ”

“ He has explicitly told me that he's trying to get our parents "onside" to either send me to conversion therapy or get me kicked out. He also openly threatens and blackmails me. ”

Perpetrators

In the survey, for each form of violence asked about, young people were also asked who perpetrated the behaviour. Figure 14 shows a summary of the people who perpetrated these behaviours, alongside quotes from young people providing further detail.

Figure 14: Reports of who perpetrated gender-based violence and/ or hate crime.

Perpetrators

Findings of the survey highlighted differences in the perpetrators of the different forms of violence. Across the different forms of violence, the majority of incidences were perpetrated by people known to the victim. Compared to other forms of violence, incidences of sexual harassment and hate crime were more likely to be perpetrated by a stranger, see Table 1.

Table 1: Reports of who perpetrated the gender-based violence and/ or hate crime.

	Sexual Harassment (N=87)	Stalking (N=51)	Sexual Assault (N=20)	Hate Crime (N=27)
Acquaintances	21% (N=18)	24% (N=12)	20% (N=4)	11% (N=3)
CoWorkers	13% (N=11)	8% (N=4)	5% (N=1)	11% (N=3)
Family	5% (N=4)	2% (N=1)	(N=0)	11% (N=3)
Friends	28% (N=24)	18% (N=9)	20%(N=4)	19% (N=5)
Partners/ ex-partners	7% (N=6)	25% (N=13)	15% (N=3)	(N=0)
Strangers	53% (N=46)	14% (N=7)	30% (N=6)	59% (N=16)

Note: Percentages will exceed 100% as participants could report multiple incidences of gender-based violence and hate-crime.

Reporting experiences of gender-based violence and hate crime

The following section of the report provides an overview of young peoples' experiences of reporting gender-based violence and hate crime. The findings are taken from our survey. Please see page 8 for an overview of how many young people participated in our survey.

Alongside the statistics on reporting experiences of Hate Crime and Gender-Based violence we include direct quotations from young people on the reasons for and for not reporting their experiences.

Reporting

In the survey, for each form of violence asked about, young people were also asked whether they had reported their experiences. The findings of this analysis are shown in Figure 15, which highlights how a higher proportion of those who experienced sexual harassment reported their experiences, compared to the other behaviours experienced.

Figure 15: The proportion of young people *who reported* gender-based violence and hate crime, presented by type of violence experienced.

Reporting

In the survey, for each form of violence asked about, young people were also asked whether they had reported their experiences and who they reported their experiences to, see Table 2. For all behaviours, the most frequently reported people told were 1) friends and 2) family members. The frequency of reporting experiences to the police ranged from 0 (for sexual assault) to 12% for experiences of stalking.

Table 2: Reports of who young people reported their experiences to.

	Sexual Harassment (N=48)	Stalking (N=51)	Partner Violence (N=21)	Sexual Assault (N=15)	Hate Crime (N=27)
Family	46% (N=22)	43% (N=22)	38% (N=8)	20% (N=3)	37% (N=10)
Friends	56% (N=27)	27% (N=14)	48% (N=10)	67% (N=10)	48% (N=13)
Partner/ Ex-partner	21% (N=10)	6% (N=3)	10% (N=2)	(N=0)	(N=0)
Manager/ Coworkers	4% (N=2)	10% (N=5)	(N=0)	(N=0)	7% (N=2)
Police	2% (N=1)	12% (N=6)	5% (N=1)	(N=0)	4% (N=1)
Other	8% (N=4)	6% (N=3)	10% (N=2)	33% (N=5)	15% (N=4)

Note: Percentages will exceed 100% as participants could report multiple incidences of gender-based violence and hatecrime and multiple people told.

Examples of 'other' people told included: reporting the behaviour on an app, telling a therapist, university supervisor (tutor), people at school, security, and flatmates.

Reporting

Below we provide some examples of young peoples' experiences of reporting their experiences of gender-based violence and hate crime.

Regarding their reporting of sexual assault, they spoke with "Sexual health clinic nurse and friend I was with on night"

Regarding their reporting of sexual assault, they spoke to "A friend. I was just laughed at".

Regarding their experiences of stalking "it was creepy, told my mum".

Regarding their experiences of sexual harassment "I told my sibling which he in turn passed a stern warning to him."

I reported the issue [*partner violence*] to school because my now ex partner had been really aggressive and made attempts to physically attack me.

Regarding their reporting of the hate crime they experienced "My parents. They didn't care. My friends, who can't do anything, and my teachers, who also can't do anything."

Not Reporting

We also analysed the data showing the prevalence of not reporting experiences of gender-based violence and hate crime. As shown in Figure 16, a higher proportion of those who experienced stalking did not report their experiences, compared to other forms of violence.

Figure 16: The proportion of young people who had *not reported* their experiences

Why did participants not report their experiences?

Participants were also asked whether they had told anyone about their experiences, and if not, why. The overriding response for not reporting their experiences was participants '**playing down**' (Didn't affect me too much) or '**normalising**' (it happens to a lot of people and there are more serious matters, it's become so normalised that it's not seen as something to tell people cos it's just everyday experience) the harm.

However, in this narrative, there were issues of **not being believed or taken seriously** (this was particularly evident in the young 16/18 group), that 'it was not worth reporting' or 'more trouble than it's worth'. **Shame, embarrassment**, and a general **lack of knowledge about where to go or who to speak to** also factored into not telling others about the harm.

Reporting

Below we provide some examples of young peoples' reasons for not reporting their experiences of gender-based violence and hate crime.

As it was a stranger, I chalked these up to unpleasant experiences [sexual harassment] I'd rather not dwell on.

I wouldn't know where to go.

None [incidences of partner violence] were deemed serious enough to me that I would need to report them

I felt ashamed following the experience [of hate crime], weak for not retaliating in some way and it made me feel powerless.

It [sexual harassment] didn't feel like it was severe enough to talk about.

I wasn't significantly affected [by the sexual harassment] personally and was able to move on - I felt it would be more trouble than it's worth.

I think its easier to keep things private.

Shame, don't want to blow out of proportion/come across as dramatic.

Embarrassing.

The impact of gender-based violence and hate crime

This section of the report outlines the impact of gender-based violence and hate crime on poor mental health, and on feelings of blame, shame and guilt.

The findings are taken from our survey, and specifically, those who reported experiencing gender-based violence and hate crime.

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Poor Mental Health

The survey also included a measure of symptoms of depression. Scores of depressive symptoms were compared between victims (N=128) and non-victims (N=27). As Figure 17 shows, victims reported poorer mental health (more depressive symptoms) compared to non-victims.

Figure 17: Mean Depressive Symptomology scores, compared by victim status.

Differences in depressive symptomology scores were examined with a Mann-Whitney U test. A significant difference was found, with “victims” reporting a higher depressive symptoms score (M= 10.91 SD = 6.26) compared to “Non-Victims” (M=8.07 SD = 4.73); U = 1,223.00 p=.017.

Thoughts & Feelings

Young people were also asked about any feelings of blame or shame they may have felt as a result of their experiences of gender-based violence and hate crime, see Figure 18. The percentages presented here are of the 137 young people who reported having experienced gender-based violence and/or hate crime in the past two years.

Figure 18: Thoughts and feelings reported by those who had reported experiencing gender-based violence and/or hate crime.

Thoughts & Feelings

The survey also included a section on trauma-related thoughts and feelings young people may have experienced, see Figure 19. The percentages presented here are of the 137 young people who reported experiencing gender-based violence and/or hate crime.

Figure 19: Thoughts and feelings reported by those who had reported experiencing gender-based violence and/or hate crime.

Thoughts & Feelings

At the end of the survey, young people who had experienced gender-based violence and/or hate crime were provided with the opportunity to share their thoughts on the impact of their experiences. Some of these stories are shared below.

“ I have had time to heal since my experiences so have overcome a lot of the negative feelings surrounding it. ”

“ I have to continue to believe that I have a future beyond this, but it gets difficult. ”

“ It actually didnt bother me as much as I thought it would, my boyfriend at the time was annoyed because he felt he should have protected me. It didnt put me off going out as such but it did make me a little wary while I was out but I could still go out and enjoy myself. ”

“ I initially blamed myself because I did kiss them back, but they came at me so quickly I had no time to think if it was what I wanted, as well as the fact that I was drunk, I didn't know what to do other than kiss them back ”

Summary

This final section of the report summarises the key findings of our project alongside next steps for our All About Respect Project.

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Summary

Over the past two academic years, we have engaged with young people in several ways, including through targeted early education events, focus groups, and our survey. Through this work, we have discussed the nature and impact of gender-based violence and hate crime, alongside strategies that young people think can be used to tackle these behaviours.

Through our work, we have identified:

Gender-based violence and hate crime happen everywhere.

Young people have explained to us that gender-based violence and hate crime can happen anywhere. They highlighted the prolific nature of these behaviours online, as well as during nights out and at work. Our Artivism project highlighted the fears young people have around street harassment and being out alone at night, while our focus group data highlighted the intrusive nature of harassment online.

Gender-based violence and hate crime are expected. Our focus group data highlight how young people feel that gender-based violence has become so normalised that they now expect to experience these behaviours. These findings are echoed in our survey. While approximately 80% felt they could tackle the behaviour, approximately a fifth of young people felt there was nothing they could do to tackle these behaviours.

Blame, guilt and shame are frequently experienced feelings for young people who report being victimised. Through our survey, we identified that young people who had been victimised reported frequent feelings of blame, guilt and shame about their experiences, with some reporting that their experiences impacted their feelings of safety and trust.

Summary

Through our work we have also identified:

Some young people don't report their experiences. The findings of our survey highlight that quite a high proportion of young people don't report their experiences of gender-based violence and hate crime. Feeling embarrassed and not wanting to 'make a big deal of it' were common reasons for not reporting. When young people report it is typically to a parent, other family member or a friend.

Ex-partners feature frequently in young peoples' experiences of gender-based violence. This is particularly the case regarding stalking and partner violence. This may suggest that young people need more guidance on ending relationships with respect.

Education needs to come earlier. Focus group and event data highlight the need for education on the topic. In our focus groups, young people shared that they prefer interactive teaching sessions rather than ones where they feel they are just being talked at.

York and North Yorkshire are safe. Data from all our activities have highlighted that, overall, York and North Yorkshire are perceived as safe places. Some areas of York have been identified as potentially unsafe, particularly poorly lit areas. However, few young people were aware of support services for gender-based violence in the region, and few had received information on how to report.

Summary

Over the past two academic years, the All About Respect project has worked with young people to find out more about their understandings and experiences of gender-based violence and hate crime.

The findings of our project have highlighted how gender-based violence and hate crime continue to be a frequent and often normalised experience for young people, both on and offline. The normalisation of these behaviours leads to young people feeling as if experiencing such violence is to be expected and inhibits their willingness to report. As our project continues to develop, we will continue to highlight that gender-based violence and hate crime are not acceptable behaviours and challenge the normalisation of such violence.

Many young peoples' experiences of violence stem from a lack of respect in their peer relationships, including a lack of respect online through what is perceived as a constant barrage of unsolicited sexual imagery, to a lack of respect in person, with sexual harassment and stalking behaviours often perpetrated by ex-partners or rejected peers. Young people told us that education needs to start earlier and include more engaging, interactive sessions that focus on relationship issues that matter to them. We plan to develop a strand of work focused on curriculum materials on respect in peer relationships to support the new Relationships Education, Relationships and Sex Education (RSE), and Health Education curriculum ([Department for Education, 2025](#)).

The normalisation of gender-based violence and hate crime highlights a desperate need for interventions that focus on raising awareness of the harm caused by such behaviours. Such interventions need to challenge common discourses that treat these behaviours as funny, a bit of banter, or just a laugh, and instead highlight their harmful and potentially illegal nature. Our newly launched Words Hurt project aims to do just this in primary schools, working with children to raise awareness of how the language we use can cause harm and how simple bystander techniques can be used to challenge such behaviours. From September 2025, we will start to roll out this work in secondary schools.

Finally, as a network, we will continue to support and highlight the work of other partners working with young people on projects to tackle gender-based violence and hate crime in York. For example, we will continue to support York College in the development of their *Call it Out* project, and with Women Unlocked on their project to raise awareness of the importance of reporting.

Our project has enabled us to work with young people across the city to find out more about their understanding and experiences of gender-based violence and hate crime. We will now use this work to inform the next stages of our project and continue supporting young people in developing and managing healthy and safe relationships, underpinned by respect.

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**Mags Godderidge
Survive**

**Sherrie Wood
Kyra**

Instagram

allaboutrespectyork

Email Address

allaboutrespectyork@gmail.com

Website

<https://sites.google.com/york.ac.uk/allaboutrespect/home>

